

Driving Compliance: The Impact of Service Quality, Tax Sanctions, Tax Compliance Costs, Application of E-Filing, and Tax Knowledge on Individual Taxpayers Compliance

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the effects of service quality, tax compliance costs, tax sanctions, the application of e-filing, and tax knowledge on compliance among individual taxpayers. The study adopts a quantitative approach and was conducted at KPP Pratama Surakarta with a sample size of 87 respondents. Primary data were collected through a questionnaire-based survey. Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) was employed for data analysis. The findings reveal that tax sanctions and the application of e-filing significantly influence taxpayer compliance, whereas service quality, tax compliance costs, and tax knowledge do not.

Keywords: Service quality, Tax sanctions, Tax compliance cost, Application of e-filing, Tax knowledge, Individual taxpayer compliance.

1. Introduction

The sources of state revenue used to finance government expenditures and national development include tax revenues and non-tax revenues. Tax revenue is a mandatory contribution from individuals or entities to the state, imposed by law, without direct compensation, and used for national purposes to maximize public welfare (Gobena, 2023; Schwebke et al., 2024). Non-tax revenues encompass fees, profits from state enterprises, fines and confiscations, money printing, loans from other countries, donations, gifts, grants, prize draw proceeds, central government revenue, and local government revenue.

Taxes are the largest source of revenue in Indonesia and remain the mainstay of state income. Tax revenues have been increasing year by year (Hermanto et al., 2022; Nuryanah, and Gunawan, 2022). Taxes are a crucial tool for the government to achieve economic, political, and social objectives, supporting various goals such as: (1) Sourcing funds from the private sector to the government sector; (2) Fairly distributing government burdens across different income classes (vertical equity) and equally among people with the same income (horizontal equity); (3) Promoting economic growth, price stabilization, and expanding job opportunities. Given the significant role of taxes in state revenue, the government should maximize income from the tax sector.

To support state revenue in the tax sector, good service to taxpayers is essential (Okoh et al., 2024; Walton, 2024). Good service is expected to increase taxpayer satisfaction, thereby enhancing their compliance with tax obligations. One way to ensure taxpayers receive adequate tax information services is through an official website from the Tax Service Office. An official website is expected to provide taxpayers with easy access to various tax-related information. A lack of responsiveness from tax service institutions in providing tax information and addressing taxpayer needs can lead to decreased compliance. Tax services are often perceived

as not adequately addressing taxpayer questions and complaints, causing confusion and reluctance in fulfilling tax duties.

Tax sanctions are necessary to increase taxpayer discipline, requiring strict sanctions for non-compliance. Tax sanctions and the use of the e-filing system in tax administration can potentially influence taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their obligations as citizens (Schwebke, 2024). In May 2004, through the Director General of Taxes Decision Number Kep-88/PJ/2004, the e-filing product was officially launched. On January 24, 2005, at the Presidential Office, the President of the Republic of Indonesia, along with the Directorate General of Taxes, launched the e-filing system. E-filing is a service for electronically filing and submitting tax returns in real-time to the Directorate General of Taxes via the internet on the Directorate General of Taxes' website or through Application Service Providers designated by the Directorate General of Taxes. The implementation of the e-filing system aims to provide convenience and ease for taxpayers in preparing and submitting their tax returns, as they can be submitted anytime and anywhere, minimizing the costs and time spent on tax calculations, filings, and submissions. E-filing reduces costs and time as tax returns can be submitted 24/7 from any location using a computer connected to the internet, eliminating the need to visit a tax office (Brink and Hansen, 2020).

Indonesia's self-assessment system requires every taxpayer who meets subjective and objective criteria to register for a Taxpayer Identification Number (NPWP). Once registered, taxpayers calculate their taxes, pay them at a bank or post office, and report them (submit tax returns) at the Tax Office where they are registered. If taxpayers are late in paying and/or reporting their tax returns, they are subject to tax sanctions. Sanctions for non-compliance with tax regulations include administrative sanctions, criminal sanctions, or both. Administrative sanctions for tax violations include interest, fines, or increases. Criminal sanctions can include criminal fines, imprisonment, or incarceration. Various tax sanctions imposed on non-

compliant taxpayers are considered burdensome, causing many to be reluctant to fulfill their tax obligations.

In recent years, a notable phenomenon in Indonesia has been the increase in taxpayers reporting previously unreported taxes. Responding to this phenomenon, the government introduced the “sunset policy” in 2008, which offers tax facilities in the form of the elimination of tax administrative sanctions, such as interest, as stipulated in Article 37A of the General Tax Provisions and Procedures Law (Law Number 28 of 2007).

The study aims to investigate the impact of service quality, tax sanctions, tax compliance costs, application of e-filing, and tax knowledge on personal taxpayer compliance. The quality of service provided by tax authorities is crucial as it can influence taxpayers’ willingness to comply with tax regulations. Furthermore, the severity and consistency of tax sanctions are expected to affect compliance behaviors significantly. The costs associated with tax compliance, including the time and effort expended, are also likely to influence taxpayers decisions to comply. Additionally, the application of e-filing systems and taxpayers’ level of tax knowledge are anticipated to play pivotal roles in shaping compliance levels among individual taxpayers.

By examining these factors comprehensively, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of the complex dynamics that influence taxpayer compliance. The findings could provide valuable insights for tax authorities in designing effective policies and strategies to enhance compliance rates among individual taxpayers. Moreover, understanding these influences can aid in the development of targeted interventions aimed at improving service delivery, refining penalty structures, optimizing e-filing processes, and enhancing taxpayer education initiatives to foster greater compliance with tax obligations.

The rest of this article is structured as follows. We begin with the theoretical background, proposed hypotheses and research methods used. This section is followed by our empirical findings and a final section which discusses implications for theory and practice.

2. Theoretical Background and Hypotheses

2.1. Theory of Planned Behavior

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), as articulated by Ajzen (1991), offers a comprehensive psychological model to explore how various factors influence the compliance behavior of individual taxpayers, particularly concerning service quality, tax sanctions, tax compliance costs, application of e-filing, and tax knowledge. TPB posits that individual behavior, including taxpayer compliance, is primarily driven by three key determinants: attitudes towards the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

Firstly, attitudes towards compliance behavior are shaped by an individual's beliefs about the outcomes of complying or not complying with tax regulations. For instance, if taxpayers perceive that filing taxes accurately and on time leads to benefits such as avoiding sanctions or maintaining a good relationship with tax authorities, they are more likely to exhibit compliant behavior. Conversely, negative attitudes towards compliance, perhaps due to perceived unfairness in tax policies or distrust in tax administration, may undermine compliance efforts.

Secondly, subjective norms play a crucial role in TPB by reflecting the perceived social pressures and expectations surrounding tax compliance. Taxpayers are influenced by the beliefs of significant others, such as peers, family members, and community leaders, regarding the importance of tax compliance. If societal norms strongly emphasize the moral obligation to pay taxes correctly and timely, individuals are more likely to conform to these norms, fostering compliant behavior. Conversely, if there is a prevalent perception that tax evasion is

acceptable or that many others are non-compliant without consequence, it may reduce the perceived social pressure to comply.

Thirdly, perceived behavioral control refers to the extent to which individuals believe they have the resources, knowledge, and ability to comply with tax obligations. This component encompasses factors such as tax knowledge, understanding of e-filing systems, ease of access to tax information, and the perceived costs associated with compliance (e.g., time, effort, financial costs). If taxpayers feel confident in their ability to navigate tax regulations and systems efficiently (high perceived control), they are more likely to engage in compliant behavior. Conversely, obstacles such as complex tax procedures, high tax compliance costs relative to income, or inadequate support for e-filing may diminish perceived control and deter compliance efforts.

Moreover, the integration of service quality into the TPB framework is pivotal, as it directly influences taxpayers' perceptions of their interactions with tax authorities. High-quality service, characterized by responsiveness, clarity of information, and assistance in compliance procedures, can enhance positive attitudes towards compliance and foster trust in tax administration. Conversely, poor service quality, such as delays in responses, unclear guidance, or inconsistent enforcement, may undermine taxpayers' motivation to comply and lead to frustration or resistance.

In conclusion, TPB provides a robust theoretical lens to understand how service quality, tax sanctions, tax compliance costs, e-filing systems, and tax knowledge collectively shape individual taxpayer compliance behavior. By examining attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control within the context of these factors, policymakers and tax authorities can develop targeted strategies to promote voluntary compliance, enhance taxpayer satisfaction, and improve overall tax administration effectiveness. This approach not only

addresses the psychological underpinnings of compliance behavior but also supports efforts to build a fair and efficient tax system that benefits both taxpayers and society at large.

2.2. The effect of service quality on individual taxpayer compliance

Service quality refers to the perceived effectiveness, efficiency, and fairness of interactions between taxpayers and tax authorities. When tax authorities provide high-quality service, characterized by responsiveness, clarity of information, and support in compliance procedures, it can positively influence taxpayer behavior and compliance outcomes (Okoh et al., 2024) Walton, 2024). Research has consistently shown that positive interactions with tax authorities lead to higher levels of taxpayer satisfaction and compliance (Doxey et al., 2021; Schwebke et al., 2024). For instance, taxpayers who receive timely assistance, accurate information, and fair treatment are more likely to view compliance with tax regulations as a straightforward and beneficial process. Conversely, poor service quality—such as delays in response times, confusing guidance, or perceived unfairness in enforcement—can undermine taxpayer trust and willingness to comply.

The relationship between service quality and taxpayer compliance can be understood through various psychological and economic theories. According to theories like social exchange theory, individuals tend to reciprocate positive treatment received from authorities by complying with societal norms and regulations. Therefore, when tax authorities demonstrate professionalism and fairness in their interactions, taxpayers are more inclined to reciprocate with compliant behavior. Moreover, organizational justice theory suggests that perceptions of fairness and procedural justice in administrative processes influence compliance attitudes. When taxpayers perceive that tax authorities treat them fairly and equitably, they are more likely to comply willingly with tax obligations, viewing compliance as a fair exchange for the services provided. Thus, we hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): *Service quality positively influence individual taxpayer compliance.*

2.3. *The impact of tax sanctions on individual taxpayer compliance*

Tax sanctions are penalties imposed by tax authorities to deter non-compliance with tax regulations, and their effectiveness in promoting compliance has been extensively studied. Research by Hayat et al. (2022) and Khozen and Setyowati (2023) underscores the significant impact of sanctions on taxpayer behavior, indicating that the severity and certainty of sanctions influence compliance rates..

According to TPB, attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control are key determinants of behavior. In the context of tax compliance, the perceived severity of tax sanctions can influence attitudes toward compliance. Higher sanctions for non-compliance may lead taxpayers to perceive greater consequences for evading taxes, thereby increasing their motivation to comply (Ajzen, 2005). Moreover, the certainty of enforcement—how likely taxpayers believe they will be caught and penalized for non-compliance—also affects behavioral intentions. When sanctions are consistently enforced, taxpayers perceive a higher likelihood of detection and punishment, which strengthens the normative influence to comply with tax laws.

Furthermore, the fairness and consistency of penalty imposition are crucial factors influencing compliance behavior. Taxpayers are more likely to comply voluntarily when sanctions are perceived as fair and applied consistently across all taxpayers. Research by Cuccia et al. (2022) suggests that fairness perceptions in tax administration positively impact compliance behavior. Thus, we hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 2 (H2): *Tax sanctions positively influence individual taxpayer compliance.*

2.4. *The influence of tax compliance costs on individual taxpayer compliance*

Tax compliance costs encompass both financial burdens, such as tax preparation fees and penalties, and non-financial burdens, including the time and effort required for tax compliance activities. Research by Hayat et al. (2022) and Khozen and Setyowati (2023) highlights the significant impact of these costs on taxpayer behavior, indicating that excessive costs can deter compliance and lead to increased tax evasion.

TPB posits that attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influence behavior. In the context of tax compliance, high tax compliance costs can affect these factors in various ways. Financially burdensome tax compliance costs may reduce taxpayers' perceived control over their tax obligations, leading to decreased motivation to comply voluntarily (Ajzen, 1991). Moreover, non-financial costs, such as the complexity of tax laws and the time required for compliance, can diminish taxpayers' attitudes toward compliance, making it less likely for them to engage in timely and accurate tax reporting.

Furthermore, the perceived fairness of tax compliance costs is crucial in shaping taxpayer compliance behavior. Taxpayers are more inclined to comply when they perceive that the costs associated with compliance are justified and equitable relative to the benefits received from public services funded by taxes. Research by Iyer and Kaszak (2022) suggests that fairness perceptions in tax policies positively influence compliance behavior. Thus, we hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Tax compliance costs positively influence individual taxpayer compliance.

2.5. The effect of e-filing on individual taxpayer compliance

The effect of electronic filing (e-filing) on taxpayer compliance is a topic of considerable interest in tax administration research (Brink and Hansen, 2020; Schwebke, 2024). E-filing systems have been widely adopted by tax authorities worldwide as they offer numerous benefits that can potentially enhance compliance behavior among taxpayers.

Previous research, such as studies by Nuryanah and Gunawan (2022) and Schwebke (2024), has highlighted these benefits and their impact on compliance rates. According to the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which posits that attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influence behavior, e-filing can exert a positive influence on compliance through various mechanisms.

Firstly, e-filing improves the convenience and accessibility of tax filing processes. Taxpayers can submit their returns electronically from anywhere with an internet connection, reducing the logistical barriers associated with traditional paper-based methods. This ease of use is theorized by TPB to enhance perceived behavioral control over tax compliance tasks. When taxpayers perceive that filing taxes electronically is straightforward and manageable, they are more likely to comply willingly and promptly (Ajzen, 2005). Research suggests that this convenience factor can lead to increased compliance rates as taxpayers find it easier to fulfill their tax obligations accurately and on time (Nuryanah and Gunawan, 2022).

Secondly, e-filing systems often incorporate features that promote accuracy and reduce errors in tax reporting. Built-in validation checks and error prompts help taxpayers ensure that their filings are complete and correct, minimizing the risk of unintentional non-compliance. TPB suggests that when individuals believe they have the necessary resources and capabilities to perform a behavior—in this case, accurate tax reporting—they are more likely to engage in that behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Therefore, the perceived ease and reliability of e-filing systems can foster positive attitudes towards compliance and reinforce compliance norms among taxpayers.

Furthermore, the transparency and feedback mechanisms inherent in e-filing platforms contribute to improved compliance outcomes. Taxpayers receive immediate confirmation of their submissions, notifications of any discrepancies or missing information, and updates on the status of their filings or refunds. This real-time interaction fosters trust in the tax

administration process and enhances compliance by ensuring taxpayers are well-informed and engaged throughout the filing process (Hermanto et al., 2022; Schwebke, 2024). Moreover, tax authorities benefit from enhanced data accuracy and efficiency in processing returns, enabling more effective monitoring and enforcement of compliance. Thus, we hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Application of e-filing positively influence individual taxpayer compliance.

2.6. The impact of tax knowledge on individual taxpayer compliance

Tax knowledge refers to taxpayers' understanding of tax laws, regulations, and their obligations, which influences their compliance behavior. Research by Hayat et al. (2022) and Schwebke et al. (2024) has highlighted the importance of tax knowledge in shaping compliance outcomes, suggesting that better-informed taxpayers are more likely to comply with tax regulations.

In the context of tax compliance, individuals with greater tax knowledge are likely to have more positive attitudes toward compliance. They may perceive tax obligations as fair and necessary, leading to stronger intentions to comply voluntarily (Ajzen, 2005). Moreover, tax knowledge enhances perceived behavioral control by providing taxpayers with the information and skills necessary to navigate tax requirements accurately and confidently.

Taxpayers who are knowledgeable about tax laws may be more aware of societal expectations and norms regarding tax compliance. They are more likely to perceive compliance as socially desirable and may face stronger social pressures to comply with tax regulations (Doxey et al., 2021; Schwebke et al., 2024). Thus, we hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 5 (H5): tax knowledge positively influence individual taxpayer compliance.

Figure 1 illustrates the theoretical model.

Figure 1. Research Model.

3. Research Methods

3.1. Participants and procedures

The population in this study consists of individual taxpayers registered at KPP Pratama Surakarta. Convenience sampling was employed to select participants, involving individuals approached randomly from those present in the same location. This sampling method was chosen for its practicality and accessibility to researchers. The sample includes individual taxpayers registered at the Surakarta Tax Service Office who meet the following criteria: (1) Individuals who possess a Taxpayer Identification Number (NPWP) and utilize e-filing; (2) Individuals residing within the Surakarta area. Data was collected through the Google Forms (<https://docs.google.com/forms/>). Our sample population includes over 10,000 individual taxpayers. Our final sample consisted of 233 eligible taxpayers.

For this study, the survey was conducted from October to November 2023. Individual taxpayers were invited to participate through personalized email invitations, which included

unique survey links and detailed instructions for survey completion. Participants were given one month to complete the survey, with a 3-day extension provided. To enhance response rates, weekly reminder emails were sent to those who had not responded.

On the day of the survey deadline, we had received 124 completed questionnaires. After conducting a detailed examination, we excluded 37 respondents due to incomplete information or missing data, resulting in a final response rate of 37.34%. According to a study by Holtom et al. (2022), which examined response rates in surveys over several decades, this response rate is considered relatively high and is consistent with typical rates observed in organizational research.

According to Cox and Holcomb (2022), the demographic profile of the survey participants is as follows. In terms of gender, the majority of respondents are male, comprising 60.927%, while females account for 39.1%. Regarding age distribution, the largest group of respondents (46%) falls within the 36 to 40 years old category, followed by those aged 41 to 45 years (23.1%), and individuals aged 31 to 35 years (13.8%). Moreover, 42.5% of respondents identified themselves as entrepreneurs, with the remaining 30% and 21.8% being employees and civil servants, respectively. In relation to educational attainment, the largest segment of participants held a bachelor's degree, representing 48.2% of the sample.

3.2. Measures

The measurement items for each variable in this study were adapted from established research sources with validated scales and rigorous testing procedures (DeVellis, 2022). A total of approximately 33 pertinent questions were selected to gauge the latent variables within the proposed model. To ensure the adequacy of these items in capturing the essence of each construct, principal component analysis (PCA) via factor analysis was employed. This analysis, conducted using IBM SPSS 29.0 software, revealed Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling

Adequacy (KMO-MSA) values exceeding 0.50 for each latent variable, with one component extracted. Additionally, all items demonstrated factor loading values exceeding 0.606, and Cronbach's alpha coefficients for each construct surpassed 0.789 (refer to Table 1), affirming the measurement of a single factor (Hair et al., 2019; Newbold et al., 2023).

Each variable—namely, service quality (SQ), tax sanctions (TP), tax compliance costs (CC), application of e-filing (EF), tax knowledge (TK), and individual taxpayer compliance (IT)—was assessed using multiple items. Respondents were instructed to rate these items on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 denoting “strongly disagree” to 5 indicating “strongly agree.”.

3.3. Data analysis

In this study, data analysis and hypothesis testing were conducted using partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). PLS-SEM is suitable for exploring complex relationships among variables and is particularly effective when dealing with small sample sizes or non-normal data distributions. It allows for the simultaneous assessment of direct and indirect effects among variables, providing insights into how service quality, tax sanctions, tax compliance costs, application of e-filing, and tax knowledge collectively influence individual taxpayer behavior. By analyzing these constructs through PLS-SEM, the study aims to uncover the key drivers of taxpayer compliance and elucidate the interplay between various factors impacting tax compliance decisions.

4. Results

The PLS-SEM analysis was performed using SmartPLS 4 software (Venturini et al., 2023). To assess non-response bias, we conducted *t*-tests comparing early and late survey respondents, as recommended by Scheaf et al. (2023). Our findings indicated no significant differences between these two groups. Based on these results, we can infer that our data

collection process was not influenced by non-response bias among non-participating respondents. Additionally, we addressed the potential issue of common method variance (CMV) by employing the marker variable approach, endorsed by Podsakoff et al. (2024). The marker variable showed no significant correlation ($r < 0.116$, $p > 0.05$) with our focal constructs. Therefore, we can conclude that CMV did not impact our measurements and did not pose a threat to the validity of our findings.

Descriptive statistics for each variable are detailed in Table 2. The calculated mean values for all latent variables are below 5, and their standard deviations (SE) are below 2, which aligns with acceptable ranges as per Cox and Holcomb (2022). To assess collinearity, variance inflation factors (VIF) were computed for each predictor, revealing that all VIF values are below 3.3, consistent with established standards (see Table 2).

4.1. Evaluation of validity and reliability

We evaluated convergent validity using standardized factor loading (SFL) and average variance extracted (AVE) methods. Concurrently, discriminant validity was assessed using the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT and HTMT2), maximum shared variance (MSV), and average shared variance (ASV) metrics. As detailed in Table 1, all items demonstrated SFL values above 0.610, and AVE values surpassed 0.50 for all constructs. Therefore, our measurements satisfy the criteria for convergent validity (Bandalos and Finney, 2019; Garson, 2023; Hoyle, 2023). Additionally, both HTMT and HTMT2 ratios remained below 0.85, and MSV and ASV values were smaller than the AVE value, as indicated in Tables 1 and 2. Based on these findings, it is evident that our measurements meet the requirements for demonstrating divergent validity (Henseler, 2021).

In the subsequent step, we assessed construct reliability using Cronbach Alpha (α) and composite reliability (ρ_c). According to Raykov and Marcoulides (2011), values above 0.70 are

considered adequate for both measures. The outcomes of these evaluations are presented in Table 1, where it is evident that values surpassing 0.789 were obtained for both measures, affirming the reliability of our measurements.

Table 1. Results of validity and reliability evaluation.

Measurement items	Item	FA	SFL	AVE	MSV	ASV	α	ρ_c
Service Quality (SQ)				0.627	0.332	0.264	0.801	0.807
	SQ2	0.861	0.847					
	SQ3	0.795	0.782					
	SQ4	0.793	0.815					
	SQ5	0.667	0.717					
Tax Sanctions (TP)				0.534	0.251	0.163	0.825	0.833
	TP1	0.760	0.765					
	TP2	0.690	0.689					
	TP3	0.764	0.773					
	TP4	0.674	0.669					
	TP5	0.733	0.745					
	TP6	0.716	0.736					
Tax Compliance Costs (CC)				0.728	0.270	0.172	0.814	0.816
	CC4	0.692	0.810					
	CC5	0.797	0.890					
	CC6	0.826	0.858					
Application of e-Filing (EF)				0.500	0.352	0.233	0.789	0.798
	EF1	0.817	0.803					
	EF2	0.620	0.610					
	EF3	0.704	0.707					
	EF4	0.678	0.677					
	EF5	0.726	0.745					
	EF6	0.639	0.639					
Tax Knowledge (TK)				0.620	0.282	0.211	0.792	0.793
	TK2	0.745	0.758					
	TK3	0.878	0.836					
	TK4	0.656	0.767					
Individual Taxpayer Compliance (IT)				0.559	0.334	0.193	0.840	0.843
	IT1	0.770	0.756					
	IT2	0.814	0.812					
	IT3	0.756	0.753					
	IT4	0.731	0.729					
	IT5	0.606	0.631					
	IT6	0.791	0.790					

Note(s): FA = factor analysis; SFL = standardized factor loading; AVE = Average variance extracted; MSV = Maximum shared variance; ASV = Average shared variance; α = Cronbach Alpha; ρ_c = Composite reliability.

Table 2. Discriminant validity results, descriptive statistics and correlations among latent variables.

Latent variable	1	2	3	4	5	6
Tax Compliance Costs (CC)	(0.85)	0.380**	0.306**	0.517**	0.442**	0.411**
Application of E-Filing (EF)	0.534	(0.85)	0.342**	0.539**	0.499**	0.595**
Individual Taxpayer Compliance (IT)	0.430	0.509	(0.85)	0.572**	0.504**	0.373**
Service Quality (SQ)	0.670	0.610	0.642	(0.85)	0.228**	0.210**
Tax Knowledge (TK)	0.697	0.664	0.625	0.335	(0.85)	0.529**
Tax Sanctions (TP)	0.494	0.368	0.480	0.457	0.595	(0.85)
Mean	1.832	3.891	3.947	4.038	3.973	3.897
Standard Deviation (SE)	0.704	0.731	0.729	0.805	0.699	0.669
Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)	1.590	2.819	–	2.099	1.893	2.860

Note(s): Below the diagonal are the HTMT2 values. Above the diagonal are the correlation values. Diagonal and bold elements are cut-off values for HTMT2. ** The correlation of constructs is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.2. Evaluation of the full model

We assessed the full model and conducted final model estimation using bootstrapping procedures. By employing 5,000 resamples to ensure robust estimates, we examined key metrics including r -square (R^2), p -values, and t -statistics. The proposed model demonstrated an R^2 value of 0.636, which, according to Cohen et al. (2003), is considered acceptable in social science research for explaining variance.

Figure 2. Full model estimation.

4.3. Testing of hypotheses

Our model estimation results, depicted in Table 3 and Figure 2, provide empirical evidence on the direct relationships between tax sanctions (TP) and application of e-filing (EF) with individual taxpayer compliance (IT). Beta coefficients (β) of 0.369 (SE = 0.126) were observed for tax sanctions (TP) and 0.376 (SE = 0.096) for application of e-filing (EF), all significant at $p < 0.01$. These findings support hypotheses 2 (H2) and 4 (H4). However, hypotheses 1 (H1), 3 (H3), and 5 (H5) were not supported as all yielded p -values > 0.05 .

5. Discussion and conclusions

The results of our study illuminate the complex dynamics among service quality, tax sanctions, tax compliance costs, application of e-filing, and tax knowledge in influencing individuals' taxpayer compliance. First, our study demonstrates that service quality does not impact taxpayer compliance. This indicates that regardless of the quality of service provided to taxpayers, it does not affect their compliance in meeting their tax obligations. This is because taxpayers already have the intention to comply with their tax duties. Therefore, the service rendered by tax officials does not influence the level of taxpayer compliance. Our findings contrast with research conducted by Susmita and Supadmi (2016) and Prabawa (2012), which showed that service quality does influence taxpayer compliance.

Table 3. Results of hypothesis confirmation.

Connection between latent variables	Coef (β)	SE	p-value	Decision
Direct effect				
Service Quality (SQ) → Taxpayer Compliance (IT)	0.114	0.099	0.124 ^{n.s}	H1 not supported
Tax Sanctions (TP) → Taxpayer Compliance (IT)	0.369	0.126	0.002 ^{**}	H2 supported
Tax Compliance Costs (CC) → Taxpayer Compliance (IT)	0.037	0.026	0.330 ^{n.s}	H3 not supported
Application of E-Filing (EF) → Taxpayer Compliance (IT)	0.376	0.096	0.000 ^{***}	H4 supported
Tax Knowledge (TK) → Taxpayer Compliance (IT)	0.073	0.102	0.238 ^{n.s}	H5 not supported

Note(s): Coef (β) = standardized beta coefficient; * $p < 0.05$ level; ** $p < 0.01$ level; *** $p < 0.001$ level; n.s = not significant.

Second, our study demonstrates that tax sanctions influence taxpayer compliance. This means that the enforcement of tax sanctions is stringent, thereby compelling taxpayers registered at KPP Pratama Surakarta to adhere to their tax obligations. This situation arises because taxpayers registered at KPP Pratama Surakarta comprehend tax laws and opt for compliance rather than facing potentially more severe tax sanctions. Our research findings align with studies conducted by Susmita and Supadmi (2016), and Fuadi and Mangonting (2013), which illustrate that tax sanctions impact taxpayer compliance.

Third, our results indicate that tax compliance costs do not affect taxpayer compliance. This implies that regardless of whether tax compliance costs imposed on taxpayers are high or low, they do not influence taxpayers registered in complying with their tax obligations. This can occur because taxpayers feel satisfied once they have fulfilled their tax obligations, so whatever tax costs they bear to meet these obligations will not impact the level of taxpayer compliance. Our research findings differ from studies conducted by Susmita and Supadmi (2016) and Fuadi and Mangonting (2013), which demonstrate that tax compliance costs influence taxpayer compliance.

Fourth, our findings indicate that the application of e-filing impacts taxpayer compliance positively. This indicates that taxpayers registered at KPP Pratama Surakarta have effectively adopted e-filing, thereby enhancing taxpayer compliance. This is because e-filing is perceived to streamline the process of meeting tax obligations. The advantages of e-filing include rapid online submission of tax returns via the internet, real-time data reception, accessibility for taxpayers to file taxes anytime and anywhere with internet connectivity, user-friendly applications, and real-time monitoring of submitted tax reports. Our findings align with studies by Susmita and Supadmi (2016), and Hidayah (2015), which demonstrate that application of e-filing influences taxpayer compliance in fulfilling their obligations.

Finally, our study reveals that tax knowledge does not influence taxpayer compliance. This implies that the tax knowledge and understanding disseminated by KPP Pratama Surakarta do not impact taxpayer compliance. This could be because taxpayers believe that by fulfilling their tax obligations, they indirectly contribute to the country's economy. Therefore, the tax education and outreach provided by tax officials do not affect the level of taxpayer compliance. Our findings are consistent with Fernando and Warisman's (2018) study, which concluded that tax knowledge does not influence taxpayer compliance. However, they differ from the research conducted by Sudrajat and Ompusunggu (2015), which stated that tax knowledge affects taxpayer compliance..

5.1. Theoretical and practical implications

Based on the theory of planned behavior (TPB), the findings of this study offer several theoretical and practical implications for understanding individual taxpayer compliance. The TPB posits that behavioral intention, influenced by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, leads to actual behavior. In the context of this study, service quality, tax sanctions, tax compliance costs, application of e-filing, and tax knowledge were examined as factors influencing taxpayer compliance. The theoretical implications highlight that while service quality and tax knowledge did not significantly affect compliance in this study, tax sanctions and the application of e-filing were found to positively influence taxpayer compliance. This aligns with the TPB's emphasis on perceived behavioral control and external influences shaping behavioral intentions.

From a practical perspective, these findings suggest that tax authorities should prioritize effective enforcement mechanisms such as stringent sanctions to enhance compliance levels. Moreover, promoting and facilitating e-filing systems can streamline tax processes and improve compliance rates among taxpayers. However, the insignificant impact of service

quality and tax knowledge underscores the need for tax agencies to reassess their strategies for educating taxpayers. This might involve refining educational programs to emphasize the broader societal benefits of tax compliance beyond mere legal obligations. Additionally, tax authorities could enhance service delivery to foster positive taxpayer attitudes and subjective norms towards compliance. By integrating these insights into policy and practice, tax administrations can potentially optimize compliance strategies and improve overall tax collection efficiency.

5.3. Limitations and suggestions for future research

While this study provides valuable insights into the factors influencing individual taxpayer compliance, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study was conducted in a specific geographical location (KPP Pratama Surakarta), which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions or countries with different socio-economic contexts or tax systems. Second, the study relied on self-reported data from taxpayers, which might introduce response bias or social desirability bias. Third, the cross-sectional nature of the study limits the ability to establish causal relationships between the variables examined. Future research could address these limitations by conducting longitudinal studies across diverse settings to explore how these factors evolve over time and influence taxpayer compliance behavior. Additionally, qualitative research methods could provide deeper insights into the underlying motivations and perceptions of taxpayers regarding compliance behaviors, complementing quantitative analyses. Moreover, comparative studies across different tax jurisdictions could elucidate the impact of varying regulatory environments and cultural norms on taxpayer compliance strategies and outcomes. Addressing these avenues could enrich our understanding and inform more nuanced policy interventions aimed at improving taxpayer compliance globally.

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